

IMPACT OF TASK ANALYSIS STRATEGY ON MORPHEMES SKILL OF STUDENTS WITH POST-LINGUAL HEARING LOSS IN GANAKA INTERNAL SCHOOL FOR SPECIAL EDUCATION, JOS – NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of task analysis on the morphemes skill of students with post-lingual hearing loss in Ganaka Internal School for Special Education, Jos-Nigeria. The study had two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses respectively. The study adopted the quasi-experimental research type, specifically the Pretest - Post-test control group research design. The sample selected for the study were twenty students with post-lingual hearing loss. The study applied the purposive sampling technique. Morphological Construction Text Items (MCTI) and Audiological Assessment Record were used as a baseline and main instruments for the study. Both the descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analyzing the scores generated for the study. The findings are as follows: For research question one: The experimental group had a pretest mean score and a standard deviation of 0.00 ± 0.00 , post-test mean scores and a standard deviation of 40.00 ± 14.91 . While the control group had a pretest mean scores a standard deviation of 2.00 ± 4.22 and a post-test mean score and standard deviation of 14.09 ± 5.16 . Also hypothesis one had a t-value of 5.212 with a p-value of 0.00. For Research Question Two: the experimental group had a pretest mean scores and a standard deviation of 1.00 ± 2.16 , post-test mean scores a standard deviation of 63.40 ± 39.17 . While the control group had a pretest mean score and a standard deviation of 5.60 ± 4.20 , the post-test mean score and a standard deviation was 12.20 ± 4.76 . Also Hypothesis Two, had t-value of 4.103, with a p-value of 0.001. Based on the above findings: there were significant differences between students in the experimental and control groups. This is in favour of those in the experimental group. The researcher proffers some recommendations based on the outcome of the study.

Keywords: Morphological skills; Morphemes; Task analysis; Pre-lingual hearing loss; Post-lingual hearing loss

Introduction

Understanding fresh language conveys new thinking and novel ideas. Logically, people try to acquire recent ideas, recent words and recent things. Morphology is said to be the study of words, which also include principles by which they are contrived, and how they are related to each other within a conversation. Morphology is also the study of the internal organization of words, and is a core aspect of linguistic studies. It is a Greek word made up of shape, form; no=ology which means ‘the study of something. In another development, Morphemes comprise roots that exist as words by themselves but can also be categories such as offixes, that can only look as part of a monumental word.

In English, the root “catch” and the suffi-ing are both morphemes, catch may sound as its own, or it may be blended with-ing to form the new word catching (Blevins, 2016). Morphemes is the diminutive meaningful element of a linguistic term and the field of linguistic study which is committed to morphemes called morphology. The concept

of morphemes seriously play a suggestive role in the interfaces of generative grammar and theoretical construct variables:

For event semantics, sentiment that each causative morpheme must have a compositional semantic meaning (denotation), and if the aim is there, there must be a morpheme (whether null or overt). They spell out the interface with which syntactic/semantic structures are ‘‘spelled out’’ by using words or morphemes with phonological content. That can also be thought of as mental lexicon insertion into the syntactic construction (Gerner & Ling 2020). In **Event morphology**, simple words do not have an internal element but consist of one morpheme for example, work, build, run etc. These cannot be separated into tiny parts which carry significant function. While complex words have internal organization which consist of two or more morphemes. For example, worker affixes which are often added to the root work to portray a noun.

In another development, task analysis has been regarded as an important component to address complex academic tasks. Therefore, functional task analysis in special education is becoming the most proposed instructional system for teaching students with learning problems. Task analysis helps students navigate reading tasks and challenging combined reading/writing tasks. This teaching tip explains a process for critically reading and analyzing writing tasks, as well as combined reading-writing tasks, that can be immediately applied in teacher classrooms. Philippakos (2017) said that using task analysis in a classroom setting, teachers based observations and assessment, of the students, should identify a skill to teach them, identify the materials needed to teach the task and break the skill down into smaller, more manageable steps (visual skills that the students can complete independently and are uncomplicated)

Research has shown that students with hearing loss did not only face challenges in grammar construction, but also encounter general reading problems when compared with their hearing counterparts in a normal classroom setting (Owobi, 2021). Students with post-lingual hearing loss are those who lose their hearing after acquiring language, or who lost their hearing later in life. Shojael, Jafari and Gholami (2016) state that these individuals with subnormal hearing acuity suffer from consequences of hearing loss compounded by impaired speech development. Most students who became deaf before the age of 6, fall significantly behind their hearing peers in their mastery of their surrounding oral language in all its forms: Written, read, spoken, and signed. Studies have revealed that post-lingual hearing loss has a negative effect on all fields of language acquisition, but the influence on phonology, morphology and advanced vocabulary are more profound. It is based on this backdrop that the author carried out this research.

Statement of the Problem

Students with post-lingual hearing loss generally tend to experience difficulties with producing grammatical morphemes, specifically with marking plural and possessives. They seem to lag behind their hearing peers as they experience serious problems with their language skills, especially when it comes to morphological skills. Teaching English generally as a foreign language (EFL) to deaf students is more challenging than for their hearing peers. As a result, deaf students are unable to completely interpret information in the form of sounds (Khasawneh, 2021). Many a times, students with post-lingual hearing loss have difficulties with idiomatic difference between English and ASL. Also, students with post-lingual hearing loss do not learn words as fast as those who have normal hearing. They may learn concrete words like cat, jump, five, and red; they may have trouble with abstract words like before, equal to, and shy. Furthermore, the most factors that contribute to deaf students struggling with morphological rules, spelling and organization thoughts can be attributed to, firstly, deaf students often find it difficult to apply morphological rules correctly leading to a lack of motivation for writing. Secondly, the interference of the first language and over-generalization of morphological rules contribute to spelling mistakes and

morphological errors in writing. Additionally, deaf students may face difficulties in organizing their thoughts and developing topic ideas for their essays. Lack of practice, limited vocabulary, and poor understanding of morphemes also contribute to the students struggles with these aspects of writing.

Aims and Objective of the Study

The aim of the study therefore, was to determine the Impact of the Task Analysis Strategy on morphological skill of students with post-lingual hearing loss, in Ganaka International School for Special Education, Jos-Nigeria. Specific objectives of the study include:

1. To find out the pretest and post-test mean scores in simple words skill performance of students with post lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control groups.
2. To determine the pretest and post-test mean scores in complex words and skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control group.

Research Questions

1. What are the pretest and post-test mean scores in simple words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control groups?
2. What are the pretest and post-test mean scores in complex words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control groups?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant pretest and post-test mean scores differences in simple words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control groups.
2. There is no significant pretest and post-test mean scores differences in complex words skill performance of students with pre-lingual hearing loss who are in the experimental and control groups.

Methods and Procedure

Research Design

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research type, specifically, the pretest post-test control group research design. The design encouraged pretest, intervention and posttest to be conducted, however, pretest and posttest was carried on the two groups, while intervention was carried on one group. There will be no randomization of subjects selected for the study.

Population and Sample

The target population for the study focused on only students with hearing loss who are in JS1 and where special education is being practiced (Ganaka International School for Special Education, Jos-Nigeria) The population of students include 19 males and 8 females respectively, thus bringing the total population to 27 students. While the sampled size for the study were only 20 students with post-lingual hearing loss. From this size, 14 were males and 6 females in that regard. They were all between the ages of 11 -13 years old.

Pretest

A pretest was carried out on students with post-lingual hearing loss for five days. The test focused on the variable of morphemes skills; simple words and complex words respectively. Ten questions were selected from each element of morphemes skills which were responded to by the students.

Intervention

A programme of intervention was designed to improve the morphemes skills of students with post-lingual hearing loss, taught and assisted with the help of one research assistant trained in the areas of the task analysis Morphological Construction Test Item. The students were exposed to reading passages of morphemes texts of simple words and complex words each for three times and one hour in a week, between 10:30am to 11:45am; on Tuesdays, Thursdays and Fridays only. The programme lasted for only two and half months (10 weeks).

Instrumentation

The instrument that was adopted for use for pretest, intervention and post-test was the Morphological Construction Text Items (MCI). A total of two passage texts with 15 simple words and complex words each were chosen and used during the intervention process. The students perused through the passages and identified the morphemes structure in the passage.

Validity and Reliability

The instrument was subjected to expert judgments in order to ascertain their presumed relevance to the property or trait being measured by three experts. The content validity was significant as it has helped the author to ascertain the extent to which the item related significantly to the objective of the study. The Cronbach Alpha reliability index was used to estimate the stability and consistency of the instrument. The readability index of the instrument was found to be 0.911.

Results

Research Question One: What is the pre-test and post-test mean scores in simple words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in experimental and control groups?

Table 1: Pretest and Post-test Mean Scores in Simple Words Skill of Students with Post-lingual Loss in experimental and control groups

GROUPS	N	Pretest		Post-test		Pretest Mean Score Difference	Post-test Mean Score Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
EXPERIMENTAL	10	0.00	0.00	40.00	14.91	-2.00	26.00
CONTROL	10	2.00	4.22	14.09	5.16		

Table 1 shows the level to which task analysis strategies have enhanced simple words skill of students with post-lingual hearing loss. The experimental group had a pre-test mean score and a standard deviation of 0.00±0.00 and post-test mean score and a standard deviation of 40.00±14.9. While the control group had a pretest mean scores and standard deviation of 2.00±4.22, post-test mean scores and a standard deviation of 14.00±5.16. This shows that before the intervention; pretest mean score of -2.00 existed between students with post-lingual hearing loss in the experimental and control group, but after intervention a post-test mean score difference of 26.00 existed between experimental and control group in favour of the experimental group.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant pretest and post-test mean scores difference in simple words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in experimental and control groups.

Table 2: T-test Analysis of Mean Score difference in the Simple Words Skills of Students with Post lingual Hearing Loss in Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Experimental	10	40.00	14.91	18	5.212	.000
Control	10	14.09	5.16			

Table 2 revealed the t-test analysis of mean score difference in the simple words skills of students with post-lingual hearing loss in Experimental and Control groups. Students with post-lingual hearing loss in experimental group had a mean and standard deviation of 40.00 ± 14.91 , while students with post-lingual hearing loss in control group had a mean and standard deviation of 14.00 ± 5.16 , t-value of 5.212 with p-value of 0.00. Hence the p-value was less than 0.05. Consequently, there was a significant mean score disparity in the simple words skills of student with post-lingual hearing loss in the experimental and control groups after intervention. The researcher rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis.

Research Question Two: What is the pretest and post-test mean score in complex words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in experimental and control groups?

Table 3: Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores in Complex Words Skill of Students with Post-lingual Loss in Experimental and Control groups

GROUPS	N	Pretest		Post-test		Pretest Mean Score Difference	Post-test Mean Score Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
EXPERIMENTAL	10	1.00	2.16	63.40	39.17	-4.60	51.20
CONTROL	10	5.60	4.20	12.20	4.76		

Table 3 discloses the degree to which task analysis strategies have ameliorated simple words skill of students with post-lingual hearing loss. The experimental group obtained a pretest mean score and a standard deviation of 1.00 ± 2.16 and a post-test mean score and standard deviation of 63.40 ± 39.17 . While the control group had a pretest mean score and standard deviation of 5.60 ± 4.20 and a post-test mean scores and a standard deviation of 12.20 ± 4.76 preceding treatment, pretest mean scores of -4.60 existed between students with post-lingual hearing loss in the experimental and control group. However, after intervention a post-test mean scores difference of 51.20 existed between students in the experimental and control groups, which was in favour of the experimental group.

Hypotheses Two

There is no significant pretest and post-test mean scores differences in complex words skill performance of students with post-lingual hearing loss who are in experimental and control groups.

Table 4: T-test Analysis of Mean Score difference in the Complex Words Skills of Students with Post-lingual Hearing Loss in the Control and Experimental Group

Groups	n	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Experimental	10	63.40100	39.17111	18	4.103	.001
Control	10	12.2000	4.76428			

Table 4 unveils the t-test analysis of mean score difference in the complex words skills of students with post-lingual hearing loss in the Experimental and Control groups. Students with post-lingual hearing loss in the Experimental Group had a mean and standard deviation of 63.40 ± 39.17 , but students with post-lingual hearing loss in the Control Group obtained a mean and standard deviation of 12.20 ± 4.76 , t-value of 4.103 and p-value of 0.001. So as the p-value was less than 0.05, a significant mean score difference existed in the complex words skill of students with post-lingual hearing loss of students in the control and experimental group after intervention. Therefore, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and upheld the alternative.

Conclusion

Morphemes is the most significant constituent of language in the area of language study. Much dedication is accorded to morphemes itself which is termed morphological structure. For example, words in simple sentences do not have spurious edifices, but are embedded into a single morpheme. These cannot also be divided into small united areas to portray its significance. Complex words which have internal edifice do also have two or more of morphemes. Task analysis is noted to have relevant constituents which help intricate collegiate functions. Functional task analysis in special education is now becoming the most intend teaching system for educating pupils with learnings challenge. Students who have post-lingual hearing loss are those who seem deaf but might have acquired language. Also students who acquire deafness before the age of 6, decline momentarily behind their hearing peers in the mastery of oral language, both in written, reading, speaking and sign language. The Impact of post-lingual hearing loss is devastating and has negative consequences on language acquirement, but its effect on phonology, morphology and advance vocabulary is most recondite. Generally, deaf students mostly encounter some challenges in organizing their reasoning and generating topic ideas for essay writing. Also, lack of drills, confine vocabulary, and destitute knowledge of morphemes structure. It is based on this backdrop that the author carried out this research.

Recommendation

1. Curriculum planners should encourage the teaching of morphology in various special schools in Nigeria.
2. School administrators should employ the use of task analysis for teaching of morphology in schools.
3. Qualified teachers should be hired by government for the teaching of English in special schools across board.
4. Head teachers and school administrators should ensure that teaching of morphology be included as syllabus for students with hearing loss.
5. Professionals in the area of interpreters should be employed to assist teachers teaching morphology to students with hearing loss.

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